

Examining Ethical Implications of Knowledge Management in Academic Libraries

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Abstract

Background: Knowledge management (KM) has become an essential strategy for improving efficiency and effectiveness in modern organizations, including academic libraries. This paper examined the ethical implications of knowledge management in academic libraries, focusing on access to knowledge, privacy and data ethics, and intellectual property rights.

Method: This paper used extensive literature review and practical insights of successful implementations of knowledge management in examining the ethical implications of knowledge management in academic libraries.

Result/Findings: The paper elucidated the primary ethical concerns associated with knowledge management in academic libraries including privacy, data security, intellectual property rights, censorship, and accessibility. It delved into the role of technology in ethical knowledge management, professional responsibilities and advocacy of academic librarians. The PAPA model comprising Privacy, Accuracy, Property, and Accessibility provides a theoretical framework for understanding ethical challenges in knowledge management. Furthermore, the paper examined an overview of knowledge management practices and future directions of emerging ethical issues in examining ethical implications of knowledge management in academic libraries.

Conclusion: The study concludes that the ethical implications of knowledge management in academic libraries are critical to ensuring that these institutions maintain their role as equitable, inclusive, and responsible centers for information dissemination.

Recommendation: Librarians should engage in an ongoing training and retraining to prevent unethical practices in librarianship and related professions. Librarians should involve users in decision-making to encourage community engagement in academic libraries and universities.

Keywords: Academic Libraries, Ethics, Knowledge Management

Introduction

Knowledge management (KM) is a recently developed strategy that applies a range of tactics and approaches to company operations in order to handle today's business issues and boost effectiveness and efficiency. It focuses on developing and utilizing an organization's knowledge assets in order to achieve its objectives (Olubiyo & Olubiyo, 2023). The era of globalization has improved how libraries are being run compared to the traditional way. Libraries and information centers embraced knowledge management only a few years ago unlike other business (Ebisi & Arua, 2018), however, knowledge management in libraries is largely focused on providing high-quality information services that are customized to meet the needs of each user in order to enhance knowledge development, application, communication as well as making knowledge available to the right people and at the right time (Tripathy, 2022).

A library is the heartbeat of any institution where information and knowledge are stored. Libraries are experiencing globalization, economic competition, and an ICT revolution due to changes in the environment. In addition to the services libraries render, they also deliver access to knowledge in privacy and data ethics, intellectual property, copyright, diversity and inclusivity in knowledge management.

Libraries have a new outlook as a result of globalization and digitization of documents. In the 1980s, the idea of information ethics emerged to address problems that emerged in publishing firms, libraries, and other institutions (Martzoukou, 2020). Ailakhu and Kingsley (2022), emphasized that ethical issues are affecting library and information professionals locally one way or another in the 21st century. Being that knowledge management is a concept in library and information science, it is bound to get caught in the web of ethical issues like privacy and data security; intellectual property rights; digital divide and censorship. According to research conducted by Avuglah et al., (2020), librarians frequently encounter ethical misconduct, such as not knowing how to handle common issues include violations of ethical codes, engaging in unethical practices like plagiarism, nondisclosure, auto citation, duplicate submissions, duplicate publications, gifted authorship, ghost authorship, data cooking, falsification, theft, and lack of ethical approval.

Ogunode & Musa (2020) posits that federal universities are funded by the federal government, university resources and international grants and this makes them better equipped to handle challenges unlike their counterparts who fund their libraries from

through students' fees only thereby affecting their effectiveness and functionality by cutting corners. This paper therefore explores the ethical considerations such as access to knowledge, intellectual property and copyright, privacy and data ethics that are associated with knowledge management in academic libraries, the role of technology in ethical knowledge management, the professional responsibilities of academic librarians, an overview of effective knowledge management practices, future directions and some recommendations

Research questions

1. What are the primary ethical concerns associated with knowledge management in academic libraries
2. What is the role of technology in ethical knowledge management
3. What are the duties of academic librarians regarding ethics

Relevant Ethical Theory

This paper was anchored on the Privacy, Accuracy, Property, and Accessibility (PAPA) model to enhance understanding of information ethics from the perspective of people, technology, and the environment. Developed by Mason (1986), the model consists of four key components which include: Privacy, Accuracy, Property, and Accessibility.

The model defines privacy as the right to keep certain information isolated except , under legal directives. According to various perspectives, privacy or anonymity refers to the expectation of confidentiality, control over personal information, and justice (Sahid et al., 2021). Privacy can also be defined as the ability of individuals to control who has access to their personal information. It involves the right to keep certain details about oneself private and to ensure that any collected information is protected from unauthorized access, with the individual's consent. According to Mason (1986), privacy refers to determining what personal information must be shared with others, under which circumstances, and with the appropriate safeguards in place. Regardless of the situation, privacy offers a line between what should be kept private and what should be shared with others. The main forces in privacy are the growth of technology and the increased value of information for decision-making.

Accuracy

Accuracy emphasizes the responsibility of ensuring information is error-free, authentic, and reliable, with an emphasis on preventing misinformation. In today's society, where

information is used extensively, we are more vulnerable to falsehoods, and accurate information is essential for sound decision-making. Given the impact of technology and information overload, it is crucial for individuals to take responsibility in maintaining information accuracy (Baharuddin, Abdullah, & Abdullahi, 2022).

Property

Property focuses on issues of ownership, fair value in information exchange, and equitable access to resources. Who owns the information is the primary property concern. Property concerns focus on information value and ownership. There are two primary concerns with the property, including copyright and intellectual property rights, particularly with regard to ICT. Information such as copyright, patents, encryption, oaths, and confidentiality must be viewed as comprehensive of the person or organization from both a quality and quantity standpoint (Peslak, 2006).

Accessibility

Accessibility refers to the conditions under which individuals or organizations can obtain and use information, raising questions about rights, privileges, and protections. It involves not only access to data but also the ethical use of publicly available information. Mason (1986) linked literacy with accessibility, emphasizing three key skills: intellectual abilities, access to information technology, and direct access to the information itself (Masrom et al., 2011).

Primary ethical concerns associated with knowledge management in academic libraries

The primary goal of taking ethics into account when managing knowledge in academic libraries is to ensure that knowledge management, which is supposed to help people achieve their goals, doesn't actually hinder them. This is because there are ways to handle people's knowledge that will stifle the entire spectrum of knowledge processes. Some of the primary ethical concerns are as follows:-

Access to knowledge

Universal access to information is a key principle in librarianship and information science, ensuring that everyone has free access to knowledge, regardless of their background. In Nigeria, digital inequality, driven by factors such as poverty, illiteracy, and lack of infrastructure, limits access to information, making it the librarian's ethical duty to provide unbiased access to knowledge for all (Titilope, 2022). Knowledge management is rooted

in human interaction, with libraries holding valuable knowledge, but it becomes unethical to withhold useful information, raising ethical concerns about individual and library rights (Obasi & Ibeguam, 2022).

Privacy and data ethics

Privacy and data protection are fundamental ethical principles in librarianship, focusing on safeguarding users' rights to access information without scrutiny and protecting their personal identifiable information (PII). Privacy ensures the right to inquiry without interference or surveillance, while data ethics mandates librarians to secure user records and transactions (American Library Association, 2006). According to Mason (2017), privacy is threatened by two main forces: the rise of information technology with its increased surveillance and data processing capabilities, and the growing value of information for decision-making, which can expose personal details and impact one's ability to form relationships.

Intellectual property and copyright

Intellectual property (IP) refers to creations like inventions, artistic works, and designs, protected by rights such as patents, copyrights, and trade secrets (WIPO, 2015). These rights balance the protection of creators' interests with public access, and librarians help safeguard IP by preventing copyright infringement and promoting "fair use" for activities like teaching and research. In Nigeria, weak enforcement of copyright laws has led to frequent violations, raising ethical concerns among library workers (Titilope, 2022).

Role of technology in ethical knowledge management

AI has advanced capabilities like pattern recognition, data processing and knowledge synthesis which can enhance the library's automation (Claude 2024) - this improves resource accessibility, streamlines operation and ultimately boosts efficiency and outreach. However, the author stressed that automation must be balanced with ethical considerations. Haffenden et al (2023) suggested that while AI may transform the workings of the academic library to improve knowledge, it can play a key role in the future development of AI.

As AI is increasingly used in large academic libraries to manage digital resources like texts, images, and ETDs, Mannheimer et al. (2024) highlight the importance of addressing ethical concerns such as transparency, reliability, bias, privacy, consent, and accessibility.

The implementation of AI in digital knowledge systems has significant implications for librarians, with Upshall (2022) suggesting the need for specific skills to evaluate and measure AI tools, ensuring that those managing these technologies understand what questions to ask, what parameters to measure, and potential pitfalls. Amalia, Kurniawati, and Fahmi (2024) explored AI's transformative impact on library services, noting its potential to improve efficiency, personalize services, and enhance collection management, although gaps remain in AI understanding and ethical discussions (Lo, 2024). The use of AI in libraries also raises ethical concerns regarding privacy, consent, bias, and transparency, with some fearing the replacement of human intelligence and challenges related to intellectual freedom and discrimination (Mannheimer, 2024; Subaveerapandiyan & Gozali, 2024).

Professional Duties and Advocacy of Academic Librarians

Knowledge on ethical knowledge management practices is essential for promoting a culture of accountability and ethics in libraries as it enhances employees' positive perceptions of their workplace thereby improving their professional ethics. Miller-Nesbitt, (2023) suggests incorporating ethics training into library education and ongoing professional development to equip librarians for ethical challenges. As a result of AI technologies in the academic libraries, there are some major shifts in the norm that they are used to leading to ethical questions regarding surveillance, exacerbated social inequality, and threats to job security Huang, Samek, & Shiri, (2021). According to Dotson, Parker and Thomas (2022) the need for clear copyright policies is necessary to help librarians feel more confident when addressing concerns of Intellectual property, lawful use, and copyright. The authors recommend that tools and policies be created and made readily available to librarians.

Outreach initiatives, library awareness campaigns, advocacy programs, and training courses for librarians are needed to promote collaboration and knowledge management among library staff (Harna et al., 2024). When librarians advocate for the services they offer, they are in fact advocating for the value of the profession. Hicks, (2016) advised that librarians should improve their advocacy attitude, so that the society at large will change their perception of librarians and knowledge of library services (Ezeala & Hundu, 2019). Opara & Eneh, (2023) asserted that detection of plagiarism is not the solution for plagiarism but rather developing strategies that can be used will be a more permanent solution to it.

Knowledge Management Practices

The study "Strategies and Best Practices of Knowledge Management in Academic Libraries in Nigeria" by Awoneyi & Okojie (2024) outlines key strategies such as utilizing ICT facilities, providing ICT and knowledge management training, and fostering a sharing culture. These strategies help eliminate work duplication, enhance skills, and create new roles for library professionals. Dimou's (2024) empirical study on knowledge management practices at NTUA Central Library emphasizes the need to treat academic libraries as intellectual assets that must be recorded, updated, and shared for effective use, suggesting that mentoring is essential for passing down acquired knowledge.

David-West (2021) examined the role of knowledge management in academic libraries in Nigeria, emphasizing its importance in improving information retrieval, storage, and the use of advanced technologies. The study advocates for adopting knowledge innovation management and cutting-edge technologies to keep libraries relevant. Similar studies by Shropshire et al. (2020), Maleksadati et al. (2023), and Mabunda & Du Plessis (2022) highlight the successful implementation of knowledge management practices, which improve library services and create a supportive environment for academic activities in the digital era.

Ratkanthiwar et al. (2024) in their study "Use of Knowledge Management Tools for Collaborative Research and Learning in Academic Libraries" found that academic libraries are increasingly adopting Knowledge Management (KM) tools to facilitate collaboration in research and education. These tools offer structured frameworks for organizing, storing, and sharing information, enabling dynamic knowledge creation and dissemination. Similarly, Olubiyo & Olubiyo (2023) emphasized the importance of KM practices in Nigerian university libraries, highlighting their role in enhancing functions such as research, curriculum development, alumni services, and strategic planning. They argue that academic libraries leverage the knowledge and expertise of staff to provide a competitive advantage, ultimately improving efficiency, productivity, and the academic experience.

David-West (2021) explored the role of knowledge management in 21st-century academic libraries in Nigeria, highlighting its importance for improving information retrieval, storage, and the application of advanced technologies such as knowledge dissemination tools and skills for information professionals. The study advocates for the adoption of knowledge innovation management and innovative technologies to maintain the relevance of libraries. Additional studies by Shropshire et al. (2020), Maleksadati et al. (2023), and Mabunda & Du Plessis (2022) also emphasize the successful implementation of knowledge management practices, which contribute to the welfare of libraries by

enhancing service provision and fostering a conducive environment for academic activities in the digital age.

Ethical implications of knowledge management in academic libraries

AI has the ability to carry out tasks that are repetitive in nature which will reduce the librarians time on such tasks and allow more time for user training in more advanced information tools (Pence, 2022).

AI can improve library services by automating routine tasks, enhancing data analysis, and enabling remote access, allowing librarians to focus on advanced research (Pence, 2022). However, to fully leverage AI's potential, ongoing training and reskilling for librarians are essential to address challenges and keep libraries up-to-date with evolving technologies (Enakrire & Oladokun, 2024).

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Lalitha, Ramalakshmi, Gunasekaran, Murugesan, Saminasri and Rajkumar (2024), emphasized that AI is being used in some libraries for tasks like reference assistants, book sorting with robots and creating learning experiences with virtual reality. The goal is to create AI systems that mimic human thinking and actions, which has significant implications for librarianship. However, some libraries are yet to adopt this trend.

Conclusion

This paper has highlighted the transformative potential of ethical knowledge management, emphasizing the importance of aligning practices with professional values. By examining relevant ethical theories, primary ethical concerns, and the role of technology, it provides a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities in this field. AI helps automate routine tasks in libraries, allowing staff to focus on more complex activities like research support and community engagement, thus improving service quality. However, challenges such as privacy concerns, algorithmic biases, and the need for ongoing staff training must be addressed through ethical strategies and continuous evaluation. In conclusion, AI offers great potential for the future

of library services, enabling libraries to adapt and provide more innovative, user-centered services while advancing knowledge and information access.

Recommendations

Here are some recommendations for libraries to adopt:

1. Librarians should be trained and retrained on a continuous basis in order to avoid unethical practices and understand the consequences of violating professional ethics. The library administration should participate in planning ethics programmes for both the patrons and librarians.
2. The library administration should instill ethical standards in new librarians and staff during employment as this would uphold their moral behaviour in all circumstances and promote a culture of integrity across the library.
3. Libraries should practice rewarding librarians based on their adherence to ethical standards and duties that way there is a healthy competition for rewards.

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